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CHANGES TO THE ESTRADA REAL ROUTE IN MARIANA, MINAS GERAIS, AFTER THE FUNDÃO DAM COLLAPSE

Abstract. This study examines the interplay between the Estrada Real Program and the districts of Camargos, Santa Rita Durão, and the former sub-district of Bento Rodrigues, in the context of the environmental disaster triggered by the collapse of the Fundão Dam on November 5, 2015. The research focuses on the controversial proposal by the Renova Foundation – the entity currently overseeing reparations for affected communities – to relocate the Estrada Real landmark from the original site of Bento Rodrigues ("old Bento") to the resettlement area ("new Bento"). This initiative raises critical concerns, as it risks symbolically erasing the accountability of the mining corporations involved (Vale S.A., BHP Billiton, and Samarco) for the ecological and socio-cultural damage caused. Adopting a descriptive and exploratory methodology, this work employs a case study approach to analyze the post-disaster conditions of the impacted districts. Findings indicate that the displacement of the Estrada Real landmark and the creation of "new Bento" fundamentally alter the socio-territorial dynamics, exacerbating the loss of cultural memory and community identity among survivors.

Keywords: Itineraries; Camargos; Santa Rita Durão; Bento Rodrigues; environmental crime; Estrada Real da Route in Mariana

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ИЗМЕНЕНИЯ ТУРИСТСКОГО МАРШРУТА ЭСТРАДА РЕАЛ ПОСЛЕ ОБРУШЕНИЯ ДАМБЫ ФУНДАУ (МАРИАНА, МИНАС-ЖЕРАЙС)

Статья посвящена изучению влияния экологической катастрофы, произошедшей 5 ноября 2015 г. и вызвавшей прорыв дамбы Фундау на развитие проекта Эстрада Реал («Королевская дорога») в Бразилии в районах Камарго, Санта-Рита-Дуран и Бенту Родригес. Целью является изучение инициатив Фонда Ренова, ответственного за организацию ликвидации последствий и ущерба, причинённого обрушением плотины Фундау в Мариане, в части восстановления пострадавших участков маршрута, перемещения исторического знака «Эстрада Реал» из старого района Бенто в новый район, куда переселено пострадавшее от катастрофы население. Авторы статьи считают, что эти инициативы представляют собой некое намеренное стирание следов преступления, совершенного горнодобывающими компаниями Vale S.A., VHP Billiton и Samarco. Исследование носит описательно-исследовательский характер, основано на изучении текущего состояния районов, пострадавших от прорыва дамбы Фундау. В качестве вывода авторы отмечают, что формирование нового района Бенту и изменение местоположения памятного знака «Эстрада Реал» в корне меняют отношения между общиной и территорией, а это вновь способствует потере культурных взаимосвязей и идентичности пострадавшего населения.

Ключевые слова: маршрут; Камаргос; Санта-Рита-Дуран; Бенту Родригес; экологическое преступление; дорога «Эстрада Реал» в Мариане

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Introduction

This study examines the socio-environmental consequences of the Fundão Dam collapse on November 5, 2015, for the districts of Camargos and Santa Rita Durão, as well as the former sub-district of Bento Rodrigues, located in the municipality of Mariana, Minas Gerais. Recognized as one of the most severe environmental crimes in Brazilian history, the disaster – caused by mining corporations Vale S.A., BHP Billiton, and Samarco – has had lasting repercussions on one of Minas Gerais' key tourist regions, situated along the Estrada Real (Royal Road) and the Gold Circuit.

The rupture released approximately 55 million cubic meters of toxic mining waste, which:

- Destroyed Bento Rodrigues, displacing hundreds of families and claiming 19 lives;
- Contaminated rural and riverside communities along its path;
- Severely degraded the Doce River basin, a critical water and food source for millions (Zhour, 2016).

Since the disaster, affected communities have faced systemic challenges, including housing instability, psychological trauma, and institutional neglect by the responsible parties.

A contentious issue arises from the Renova Foundation – a nonprofit entity established under the Termo de Transação e Ajustamento de Conduta (TTAC) – proposing to relocate the Estrada Real's official route from the original site of Bento Rodrigues ("old Bento") to the resettlement area ("new Bento"). While framed as a measure to preserve the tourist circuit, this proposal risks erasing the historical and cultural memory of the crime, given that the original route was part of the colonial-era path governed by the Portuguese Crown.

Research Objectives

This study aims to:

- 1) Analyze the socio-territorial impacts of the 2015 environmental crime on communities linked to the Estrada Real;
- 2) Trace the historical integration of these

localities (Santa Rita Durão, Camargos, Bento Rodrigues) into the Estrada Real program;

- 3) Amplify the narratives of affected communities, emphasizing their right to memory, territory, and cultural preservation.

Despite seven years having passed since the disaster, Bento Rodrigues' residents continue to demand:

- Access to their ancestral lands ("old Bento");
- Resettlement policies that respect their lived experiences;
- Preservation of traditions tied to the Estrada Real, a cornerstone of Minas Gerais' cultural heritage.

This work underscores how the proposed route alteration silences victims' voices and whitewashes corporate accountability, further destabilizing the identity and sociability of displaced populations.

Literature Review

The Estrada Real as a way to identify the memory of places

The so-called "Estrada Real" have their origins in the 15th century when land and river routes were already considered the rights of the Portuguese crown (Pires, 2017). A few centuries before the gold rush, communication between São Paulo and the northeast of the colony was carried out through a single path that followed the São Francisco River, known as the "Caminho Geral do Sertão" (Pires, 2017). With the discovery, two new routes were created: the Caminho da Bahia or "dos currais," which followed the banks of the São Francisco River, and the Caminho Velho or "Caminho de São Paulo", which was traversed by the São Paulo bandeirantes (Pires, 2017). According to Pires (2017), from 1699, another path was being traversed by Garcia Rodrigues after a year and a half of work in the region known as Borda do Campo, which connected Rio de Janeiro to the region of Minas Gerais, shortening the distance. This route became known as the Caminho Novo or "do Garcia Rodrigues".

With the emergence of villages and

settlements and the various other internal routes that connected the main mining locations, the so-called Estrada Real were created. According to Renger (2007, p. 135), the colonial paths were given the name "Estrada Real" (Royal Road) because the state was present through checkpoints known as "registros", where they collected royal rights, such as tolls, entry fees, and royal taxes. According to Scheffel (2022), to prevent the diversion of gold along the routes, the colonial government determined that the riches should pass only through certain designated paths, collectively known as the Estrada Real.

The Estrada Real Program was and is a large project aimed at promoting tourism development in Brazil. It was the country's first tourist plan focused on a specific route (Scheffel, 2022, p. 571). The Estrada Real is the largest tourist route in the country, spanning over 1,630 kilometers through the states of Minas Gerais, Rio de Janeiro, and São Paulo. Today, it showcases the traditions of the route, highlighting the region's identity and beauty (Instituto Estrada Real, n.d). According to Pires (2017), the Estrada Real Program was developed between 1999 and 2003, launched in the city of São João Del Rei, and has since aligned with the National Tourism Plan – created by the Ministry of Tourism in 2003 – as well as with the policies of the Regional Tourism Program – Roteiros do Brasil – launched in 2004.

According to Scheffel (2022), the Estrada Real is now one of the largest ongoing tourism projects in Brazil, encompassing over 170 municipalities. "The Estrada Real has become a historical and cultural axis, covering cities, monuments, and paths that attract millions of visitors, promoting cultural, religious, and gastronomic tourism, as well as ecotourism and adventure tourism in its surroundings" (Scheffel, 2022, p. 559). Its goal is to preserve and promote the ancient paths traversed by the colonizers and the royal family, as well as to promote and value the historical and cultural heritage of the localities, stimulating tourism and the development of small towns that gain visibility and tourist attention

through this program.

According to Cardoso (2012), the category of Cultural Routes is present in the current guidelines of UNESCO for the application of the World Heritage Convention. In line with this, the Cultural Route is listed along with other categories of cultural and/or natural value, such as cultural landscapes, historic cities/centers, and heritage canals. Therefore, the preservation of these places becomes of utmost importance due to the relationship between individuals and the history that runs through their original territories, which aligns with the current definitions of cultural heritage, whether it is tangible or intangible, as elements that "express or reveal the memory and identity of populations and communities". These elements are composed of cultural assets of historical and/or artistic and/or scientific and/or symbolic value, which can also be tourist attractions, such as "archives, buildings, urban complexes, archaeological sites, ruins; museums and other spaces intended for the presentation or contemplation of material and immaterial goods; manifestations such as music, gastronomy, visual and performing arts, festivals, and others" (Brasil, 2007, n.d).

Therefore, the Estrada Real, beyond being a driver of tourism development, is also part of the identity and memory of various individuals who have a connection to the territories where these routes are located. According to Lara (2016), memory can be popularly understood as "the capacity that human beings have to preserve and recall experiences and information related to the past, which are part of the interaction processes of each individual with their environment." Its construction occurs as the relationships between individuals are established through their interactions, influenced by sociocultural aspects such as work environments, family, politics, religion, and so on.

Memory can be divided into two main categories: individual and collective. Halbwachs (2003) describes individual memory as "the first testimony to which we can always refer," and collective memory as "if we were facing many testimonies". Thus,

when we talk about Bento Rodrigues, we have these two analyses regarding the residents of the community. Undoubtedly, the dam breach is an event that marked the lives of the population and became a collective memory of pain, where the experienced trauma contributes to the creation of new memories.

When correlating memory with a territory, the creation of bonds and, consequently, a sense of belonging emerges from the interaction of individuals with the living space and the people around them. Memory influences the individual's particular view of places and their importance to each person. It is evident that memory plays a significant role in human life. It is through memory that identity begins to be constructed, as memories arise from day-to-day experiences. Lara (2016, p. 2) points out that "since society's own identity carries out certain selections of memory, and still shapes the predispositions that will lead the individual to incorporate certain specific aspects of the past".

Thus, it can be affirmed that memory contributes to preventing the past from falling into oblivion, and according to Le Goff (2013), it enables humans to update past information, perpetuating history in human consciousness. That being said, the next topic will address the relationship between the districts of Camargos, Santa Rita Durão, and the former sub-district of Bento Rodrigues as spaces of memory and their relation to the Estrada Real and the post-crime context.

Districts in the municipality of Mariana included in the Estrada Real affected by the crime

The district of Camargos is located near Serra do Caraça and 19 km from the center of Mariana. It is a small village that emerged when three brothers (Tomáz Lopes de Camargos, João Lopes de Camargos, and Fernando Lopes de Camargos) found gold in the stream and settled in the area. With waterfalls, lakes, natural beauty, and history, Camargos offers a pleasant space for trips and tours. To reach the district, one can leave Mariana's bus station and follow MG-129 towards the mining areas. After approximately 4

km, take a right turn towards Vila Del Rey and a left turn onto the dirt road, continuing for about 10 km. The road is narrow, winding, and unpaved, constituting a section of the Estrada Real.

Santa Rita Durão is a small village that emerged in the search for gold mines. It is located 35 km from the center of Mariana. Initially, the district was named "Inficionado", derived from "infeccionado", which indicated a small amount of gold with low quality found in the local watercourses. In 1720, the district became the birthplace of Frei Santa Rita Durão, a pioneer of Brazilian literature, known for one of the greatest poems: "Caramuru". Due to his significance to the locality, the district was named after him. To reach the district via the Estrada Real, one can use the highway that connects Mariana to Santa Bárbara (MG-129) or the path that passes through Camargos and Bento Rodrigues. According to information provided by the Estrada Real, the route is well signposted.

The community of Bento Rodrigues, a subdistrict of Santa Rita Durão, is located 24 kilometers from Mariana. In the early 18th century, the subdistrict became populated through mining activities established in the area. The path of the Estrada Real passed through the urban center of the subdistrict.

On November 5, 2015, around 4:20 p.m., the Fundão dam of Samarco S.A – a joint venture of the world's largest mining companies, the Brazilian company Vale S.A and the Anglo-Australian company BHP Billiton – suffered a rupture and collapsed (Silva & Faulhaber, 2020). The community of Bento Rodrigues was the first territory affected by the tailings due to its proximity to the dam's location. Other districts were also affected, including Paracatu de Baixo, the municipality of Barra Longa, Gesteira, and several communities in the Camargos district. According to research, approximately 55 to 60 million cubic meters of mining tailings completely buried the subdistrict, transforming Bento Rodrigues into a sea of mud.

Following the dam breach, investigations began to understand the causes of the

collapse, considering the immeasurable loss to the first affected community. According to Zhouri (2016), the various flexibilizations of environmental licensing processes have led to irreversible impacts and incalculable risks for the population and the environment in these areas. The research reports that data from an inspection conducted in 2013 identified risks to the village and recommended the implementation of "periodic geotechnical and structural monitoring of the dikes and dam" and highlighted the need for the presentation, by the entrepreneur, of a contingency plan for risk situations or accidents (Zhouri, 2016).

This corroborates Carrato's (2018) analysis of the role of Brazilian journalism regarding the dam breach, stating that "the media cannot alter reality but can significantly alter people's perception of reality". According to the author, the interests of mining companies Samarco, Vale, and BHP Billiton have had more prominence in the media since the dam breach. Despite more than seven years having passed and "evidence that the breach occurred due to negligence by these companies, the over 600 residents of Bento Rodrigues have not had their rights recognized, nor have the families of the 19 deceased individuals been compensated" (Op cit). Another virtually consensual point is that the creation of the Renova Foundation was a way for the mining companies to delay the compensation processes (Op cit):

"When you have damage caused by Samarco, it is the primary obligation along with Vale and BHP. When you create the legal entity of the foundation, you create a third party to be responsible for the damage caused by the first three. So, you have created a facade that will once again hinder enforcement in case of non-compliance. It's as if you caused harm to someone and instead of paying and repairing, you said, 'Wait a minute! I'm going to create a legal entity, a foundation that will pay you.' No one would accept this agreement, but the Union and the states of Minas Gerais and Espírito Santo accepted it" (A Sirene, 2016, p. 4).

The Renova Foundation is a non-governmental, nonprofit organization established with the purpose of implementing and managing programs for the reparation of those affected by the breach of the Fundão dam. It is responsible for addressing the necessary issues for the affected communities, including the districts of Camargos and Santa Rita Durão and the subdistrict of Bento Rodrigues, and is maintained by the joint venture, a business agreement, between two or more companies, namely Samarco, a privately held mining company owned by Vale and BHP. Among the activities proposed and carried out by the Foundation is the revitalization of the roads in these districts, as they remained inaccessible for a long time, which posed challenges for both the communities as residents and for tourists who wished to travel along the Estrada Real.

The Renova Foundation is also leading the slow process of resettlement for those affected. Even after more than seven years have passed, no houses have been delivered. In the image below (Fig. 1), you can see the location of the future districts.

A study conducted in 2016, using archaeological methods, aimed to recover part of what was previously known as Curral and Colcho Pedras. According to Santos, Ribeiro, and Pereira (2019), oral history and an internet video⁴ suggest that the mentioned space would be the livestock corral used since the late 17th century. According to the authors, in the early decades of the 19th century, Bento Rodrigues was an almost obligatory stop for travelers moving between Ouro Preto and the villages to the north along the Estrada Real: "Thus, a constructed architectural ensemble was formed, ranging from the entrance of the district, marked by the stone walls of Curral, to the chapel of São Bento, or rather, to the residence of Major Ferreira located next to the temple" (Santos, Ribeiro & Pereira, 2019, p. 5). Described as "a two-story rammed earth house, whose construction dates back to the founding of the settlement, the major's residence had its second floor dismantled in the 1960s when it was also transformed into the

Fig. 3 – Measurement of the 2.7-meter portion where the alignment of stones of the corral ends²

Fig. 4 – Stone trough revealed during the removal of the ore waste layer

Fig. 5 – Vertex of the stone corral alignment at the eastern end

According to the authors, the archaeological work carried out was the last record of the remnants of the stone corral and trough structure, as the area is currently submerged in the S4 dike area (Santos, Ribeiro & Pereira, 2019). For the purpose of knowledge, dikes are structures that serve to contain water. Due to their considerable size, the choice of dike position aims for the lowest construction cost and the highest water retention capacity. The soil beneath the structure needs to be resistant to support its weight and impermeable

to prevent water from passing underneath it (A Sirene, 2016).

The construction of Dike S4 was considered a way to destroy part of the remaining history of Bento Rodrigues. All the structures shown in the previous images are related to the colonial period of the subdistrict (Santos, Ribeiro & Pereira, 2019). The authors also emphasize that "they are part of an integrated whole that is associated with the establishment of the location as a place of residence, gold exploration in the 17th and 18th centuries, and access to other places, as the Estrada Real connected Bento Rodrigues and the Santa Rita Durão district to the Camargos district, playing a role in the formation of these settlements" (Santos, Ribeiro & Pereira, 2019, p. 15).

Supporting this, Ferreira (2017, p. 34), while analyzing the narrative among Samarco S.A., Fundação Renova, MPMG (Minas Gerais Public Prosecutor's Office), the Regional Superintendence of IPHAN (Brazilian Institute of National Historic and Artistic Heritage), and DEPHAN/IPHAN (Department of National Historic and Artistic Heritage) as described in documents, identified some divergences. While Samarco and Fundação Renova defended the chosen location for resettlement "as the most viable (and efficient) to meet the request of the Municipal Environmental Secretariat of Mariana" (Op cit), the Minas Gerais Public Prosecutor's Office and the Regional Superintendence of IPHAN, the two state entities most involved in the process, "opposed the possibility of new negative impacts in the former urban core of Bento Rodrigues, suggesting the study of other sectors for the realization of this project" (Op cit). Finally, DEPHAN/IPHAN considers that "due to the absence of federally listed assets, 'archaeological monuments,' and an ongoing listing process in the locality of Bento Rodrigues, it is not within IPHAN's jurisdiction to authorize or not authorize works in the area, as the institution has no legal responsibility for the assets or the area in question".

² Fig. 3–5 source: Equipe Arcadis, April 2016.

The district, which was once composed of architectural heritage, beautiful landscapes, and a strong identity, has been completely lost. To recover it, it is of utmost importance to establish heritage policies capable of demonstrating the full value of the site. André Silva (2020) makes observations regarding this process, which must occur on two fronts. The first is resettlement, with "the establishment of a heritage policy that rebuilds the collective memory of those affected by the dam collapse, in order to make this group visible, reference them, and give meaning to their constant struggle for the right to the past and the preservation of identities" (Silva, 2020, p. 13). At the same time, consideration must be given to the planned uses for the ruins of old Bento Rodrigues, as "the duty of memory is a form of reparation in the face of disasters resulting from actions related to the environment. It is necessary to reinforce non-forgetting by placing the affected people as the main agents in the search for recognition" (Op cit).

Reflecting on and considering the possibilities to keep the history of Bento Rodrigues alive is essential. Castriota (2019), in describing the dossier prepared for the emergency listing request of Bento Rodrigues, pointed out the need to create a territory museum. According to him, the fact that Bento Rodrigues is "a site of memory" allows for the implementation of actions so that it can also become "a site of consciousness" (Castriota, 2019, p. 364). The author also draws attention to the possibility of "analyzing the historical-cultural processes that shaped its landscape and fostering a critical stance toward the mining exploitation model and its impacts, including its responsibility for protecting natural and cultural heritage" (Op cit). A Territory Museum is a museum format in which the object transformed into a museum is not separated from its original environment, but the entire territory is treated as a museum.

Another reflection brought by Gontijo et al. (2021) is that "mining, which in the first cycle was responsible for building a large part of the region's cultural heritage, now shows

itself as a destructive activity for this same heritage." As the authors highlight, the municipalities of Mariana, Ouro Preto, Brumadinho, Barão de Cocais, and Nova Lima, all located in the Quadrilátero Ferrífero region, have suffered recent and severe impacts on tourism due to dam breaches and/or the risk of collapse of mining tailings dams. The recent chronology has its starting point in the 2015 breach in Mariana, followed by the one in Brumadinho in 2019, and the imminent risks of incidents in 2020, with the evacuation of districts and villages in Barão de Cocais, Ouro Preto, and Nova Lima. It is worth noting the agreement with the authors when they conclude that the "development projects/initiatives currently underway in the region have proven to be incompatible or even antagonistic, as in the case of mining projects and installations in relation to tourism" (Gontijo et al., 2021, p. 11).

This incompatibility, in the case of the affected districts, becomes increasingly evident. Among them is the serious impact of the loss of the proposed and implemented initial section of the Estrada Real, which negatively affects the image of the municipalities, the preservation of memory, the way of life of residents, and the circulation of tourists and locals.

Methodology

This research is descriptive and exploratory in nature, based on a case study of the current situation of individuals affected by the breach of the Fundão Dam. Part of our objectives with this work is to understand the history of the Estrada Real, the process of including localities, how their routes are determined and developed, and finally, to comprehend how the districts of Camargos, Santa Rita Durão, and the sub-district of Bento Rodrigues were incorporated into one of these routes. To achieve these objectives, bibliographic and documentary research was conducted focusing on the sites along the Estrada Real itself.

Considering that after the dam breach, the sub-district of Bento Rodrigues was completely destroyed, this study also seeks to investigate the existing relationship between

the sub-district and the districts of Camargos and Santa Rita Durão with the Estrada Real, taking into account the current possibility of changing the route from the "old Bento" to the "new Bento", the location where the re-settlement process of the families affected by the crime is taking place. This possibility will be examined through bibliographic and documentary research, as well as through news articles that address the topic, in addition to participating in meetings of the Municipal Tourism Council of Mariana (COMTUR), where it will be possible to follow the decision-making process and the narrative of the Renova Foundation regarding the reparation processes involving the affected communities.

Results and discussion

As mentioned throughout this article regarding the objectives of the Estrada Real, the idea of retracing a path taken by the royal family and valorizing the official route, which was the only one permitted by the Portuguese crown during the gold and diamond cycles, initially indicates the locations through which the journey will pass. Thus, the inclusion of Bento Rodrigues, Santa Rita Durão, and Camargos, localities that connect Ouro Preto, a region abundant in gold, to Diamantina, which was a region with significant diamond production.

When Gonçalves (2015) already highlighted the various forms of heritage, which constitute expressions and representations of identities of groups and social segments, an

important reflection begins about defending, fighting for, and preserving the public recognition of Bento Rodrigues, signifying a fight for the very existence and social and cultural continuity of the group. The return of that place ("old Bento Rodrigues") to its original community goes beyond resuming life; it is a victory to celebrate their memories. The community is still present and feels a sense of belonging to that place, and they do not feel a sense of belonging to "Nova Bento Rodrigues." Therefore, it is a place of memory, and being a place of memory is to cherish the many who are no longer here, to keep the history and lineage of a people alive, who deserve to know, pass down, tell, and serve as an example of what should never be repeated. Not recovering Bento Rodrigues for the residents is to let it fall into oblivion, and falling into oblivion "is to bear silence and indifference" (Starling, 2019).

Building on the principles of the Estrada Real, which aims to preserve the paths used during the gold and diamond cycles, the passage of this route through the districts emphasizes that this was the official route of the Portuguese crown and ensures that the region and its entire history up to the present day are valued and maintained. Therefore, for a community that is involved in tourism, continuing to have this landmark is of paramount importance both for the economic activity and for the integration of the population and the sense of belonging to a historic and touristic region (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3 – Landmark near Bento Rodrigues, photo taken in June 2015, therefore before the rupture of the Fundão Dam³

³ Source: Antônio Jr. / RETRIP

Through meetings of the Municipal Council of Tourism of Mariana (COMTUR), we were able to better understand the feelings and struggles of the communities, both in their desire to restore access that is still blocked and their dignity and the return of tourism in a way that is not reported. Much is said about environmental restoration, which is indeed important, but little is still publicized about the community, which also suffers from economic, social, and cultural damages.

On March 14, 2023, A Sirene newspaper, an important media outlet created with the purpose of fighting for the voice rights of those affected by the rupture of the Fundão Dam, made a post on the Instagram social network. It was informed that on February 11, 2023, an event took place in which the milestone of the Estrada Real was placed in the resettlement area, despite the affected people's desire for the milestone to be placed in Bento Rodrigues, its original location. Once again, they were disrespected by the Renova Foundation, Samarco, Vale, and BHP Billiton. In this way, the milestone now invents a history that never existed, considering that the route of the Estrada Real never passed through the location where it has now been inserted.

The relocation of the milestone of the Estrada Real, which passes through Bento Rodrigues, was considered by the residents as a lack of respect towards the community and its history. This change results in the erasure of the memory and formation of the site, as well as creating false information about the Estrada Real route, potentially leading to the belief that the path indeed passed through the

current location, thus fulfilling the role proposed by the companies responsible for the crime, which is to camouflage what happened.

Conclusion

Based on all the research conducted, it is important to reiterate the significance of the subdistrict of Bento Rodrigues today. In addition to its connection with the Estrada Real, it is also a place of memory, and being a place of memory also means being a place of awareness. With that said, we believe that the creation of an Ecomuseum can help keep alive the struggle for the preservation of the history, tradition, and culture of a people, as an ecomuseum is an instrument crafted, explored, and conceived by a population according to their knowledge and experiences, making this history enduring. The community of Bento Rodrigues plays a crucial role in the construction of a Territory Museum, as it is their history that needs to be told.

Considering what has been presented throughout this work, one of the best paths would indeed be the restructuring of Bento Rodrigues in its original location. Although it may take a long time, it will preserve the authenticity of the place and allow the indigenous population to return to their place of origin, thereby bringing authenticity to the Estrada Real route. Furthermore, the proposal of a Territory Museum, an Ecomuseum, would have a significant positive impact on the community of the subdistrict, as it would keep their history, culture, and tradition alive, with the community members as the protagonists.

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